

EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN METHODS IN DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPREHENSION SKILLS OF NON- PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH

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***Abstract.** This article provides information on ways to develop listening comprehension skills in English. In particular, phonemic, phonetic and intonation components of the main language are deeply interpreted in the development of listening comprehension. The article deals that the modern teaching with listening skills. Also, it is given the easy way improving languages listening skills below.*

***Keywords:** interpersonal activities, Group activities, Audio segments, Video segments , language components, linguistic and extra linguistic difficulties, language skills, audio segments, group activities, video segments, interpersonal activities.*

Listening comprehension means listening, perceiving and understanding speech. In general, "speech" means speaking, listening comprehension, reading comprehension and writing. In fact, it is better to say "listening and understanding speaking". It turns out that listening comprehension is more difficult than learning to speak. It is necessary to distinguish between two terms related to this field: "listening" - listening and "hearing" - receiving sound using the sense of hearing . Among the other four skills, listening is the one that has been most forgotten and neglected in second language classrooms. So teachers don't pay much attention to this skill and teach it carelessly. In the field of language teaching and learning proficiency has tended to be viewed as the ability of speaking and writing in language in question. Listening and reading skills are in the second position. One reason for this situation might be the demanding characteristic of the listening skill. Listening has gained a new importance in language classrooms after spreading IT technology based information in society in Iran. Moreover it should be mentioned that most of the students' class time is devoted to the listening. Despite this, we often take importance of listening for granted, and it is the most overlooked skill among other skills. In natural order of learning any language, listening stands at first rank. Without any reception one can not produce anything. Though, if a teacher wants to have fluent and productive students, he/she should pay much and necessary attention to teaching listening skill.

In order to teach listening comprehension as a practical goal, firstly, select (compose) the audio text, secondly, determine the organizational conditions for broadcasting it (belonging to a class, some group or a single student), and thirdly, prepare the student for listening. (knowledge of the language material, appropriateness of the content of the audio text), fourthly, how many times it is recommended to listen (preparation of educational tasks) and, fifthly, it requires an activity such as checking the understanding. The following method of work on the audio text is recommended: the teacher listens (reads) the audio text himself, identifies its difficult areas and thinks of ways to eliminate them, uses educational tools that support understanding (drawing, writing on the blackboard, tape recorder) prepares tasks for the first and subsequent hearings. The stages of teaching listening comprehension during a lesson are as follows.

- 1) expected difficulties in listening are eliminated;
- 2) an instruction (assignment) is given on the first hearing of the audio text;
- 3) understanding is checked with the help of a task;
- 4) a second hearing is ordered;
- 5) will be checked, etc.

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Listening-Some of the teachers believe that speaking should be actively discouraged. One of the reasons of emphasizing listening and delaying speaking is based on an opinion. Those who give importance to speaking view the language as a product and think that language is a behavior and speaking is the manifestation of this learning or happening. On the contrary, there are approaches that gave more importance to listening. In this approach of language learning, listening is at the center. All of the information necessary for building up the knowledge for using language comes from receptive skills: listening, and reading. When the knowledge of language in this regard is built the learner can write and speak. In other words, without any input, the outcome or output should be nothing. The modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercise to multimedia resources. Listening skills can best learn or improved through simple and engaging activities that focus more on the learning process instead of the final product. It doesn't matter you are working with small or large groups of students, you can use any of the following technique to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen well.

Interpersonal activities :The non-threatening and effective way for students to develop stronger listening skills can be done by interpersonal activities such as mock interviews and storytelling. Students are assigned to small groups of two or three they are given by a particular listening activity to complete. For instance, you may have an interview with a student for a job with a company or for an article in a newspaper. Even a storytelling activity can give students the opportunity to ask one other question and then practice active listening skills. Group activities Large group activities also give the opportunity to the student to help through a helpful method for teaching listening skills to students. You can also begin with a simple group activity. For the first activity, students are divided into the groups of five or more and instruct them to learn one interest or hobby of at least two other group members. It is necessary to encourage students to ask

clarifying questions during the activity and you may allow them to take notes because it is helpful. While, as time passes and their skills grow, you should limit students to only write notes after the completion of the first activity. The second part of the activity is to allow students sit in a large circle and then have each individual student to share their name and their interest hobby of the group member that they met. This second part of the activity leads to additional listening exercises.

Audio segments: You can also teach listening skills to the students through audio segments such as radio programs, instructional lectures, online podcasts, and other audio messages. It is necessary to deploy interactive listening programs in class with students and then instruct them to repeat the exercise on their own. First of all, instruct students to prepare for listening by imagining anything they want to learn from the content of the audio segment. It's on you to choose shorter or longer audio segments and you can also choose more challenging or more accessible material for this type of exercise.

Video segments: The other most helpful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments that include short sketches, documentary films, dramatic or comedic material, news programs, and interview segments. As in the audio segment, you can select the portion and length of audio you can also do it in a video segment based on the skill level of your students. First, watch the segment without any sound and discuss it together with the student. Encourage your student what they think will be the content of the segment. This will improve their listening and thinking power.

Some students complain to teachers that, although they can understand what ALTs (Assistant Language Teachers) are saying because they speak slowly and clearly, they cannot understand what native English speakers are saying in real life. Why does this problem happen? What is wrong with the teaching of listening in Japanese schools? The first and probably the biggest problem is that, although the importance of listening skills is widely acknowledged in Japan, the adequate teaching and materials to develop them have not been provided. In a typical listening lesson, students either listen just to the taped script of a reading textbook or, after listening to some materials, they answer multiple choice questions based on the content of listening materials. In this kind of lesson, correct answers are emphasized, but the listening process necessary to decode the information is ignored, and the kinds of skills and strategies for effective listening are not practiced. That is, students are just tested on their own ability to answer correctly and are not taught how to listen to English. Second, the amount of time for listening lessons is limited in English I and II, compared with reading, writing, and speaking. For example, it is estimated that the average time devoted to listening activities in every class is 5 minutes per day. Students are not sufficiently exposed to a variety of authentic materials, either. In short, although they are accustomed to English spoken clearly and slowly in classroom materials and can understand it, they get embarrassed and frustrated when they encounter real English which is spoken at a normal speed. Third, they are not used to the difference between spoken English and written English. Spoken English has different features such as ungrammatical utterances, false starts, hesitation, assimilation, and redundancy. If they aren't familiar with those phenomena, they may not be able to listen to English and understand it.

Lastly, in listening lessons, teachers don't have the specific notion that listening should be integrated with other skills, i.e., speaking, reading, and writing.[1] When real world communication is examined, we never finish verbal communication appropriately without doing

something after listening. For example, when we have a conversation with someone, we have to respond to him or her. It is never just one way communication. In a situation like a lecture in which students are listening to the instructor, they usually take notes. We can think of many other situations in which listening is integrated with the other three skills. In real world communication, that is, listening, speaking, reading, and writing are interrelated and interdependent. In conclusion, listening to special audios and passing the above six steps to improve listening comprehension skills while learning a language will certainly give effective results. In order to remember new words quickly and easily, sentences are made using them, which effectively helps in improving pronunciation and using them in oral speech.

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